

Automated image analysis of ultrafast synchrotron CT scans to experimentally characterize the fibre break development during *in-situ* tensile tests

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3D microstructure of carbon composite under load

4D analysis of fibre trajectories and link with fibre breaks

Opportunities for composite strength modelling

